

Figure S1

Figure S1. Nichoids increase the functionality of HSPCs upon *ex vivo* culture, related to Figure 1.

(A) Representative pictures of the nichoid culture substrate with CD34+ cells pre- and post-treatment with the citrate solution (left) and percentage of cells retrieved from nichoids (right) compared to conventional 2D culture. Scale bars: 200 μ m.

(B) Representative gating strategy for apoptosis analysis (left). Cells are distinguished as alive (7-AAD-Annexin V-), early apoptotic (7-AAD-Annexin V+), late apoptotic (7-AAD+Annexin V+), and necrotic (7-AAD+Annexin V-). Apoptosis analysis performed within CD34+ cells (right) treated or not with the citrate solution (n=6).

(C) Representative pictures and number of erythroid, myeloid, and mixed colonies generated in the CFU-C assay from HSPCs treated or not with the citrate solution seeded on day 1 (n=6). Scale bars: 50 μ m.

(D) Apoptosis analysis performed within CD34+ cells (n=6,6,5,5).

(E) Representative gating strategy for phenotypically defined HSPC subsets analysis. CD34+ cells were identified within alive cells from (A). HSPC subpopulations were discriminated as CD34+CD133-CD90-, CD34+CD133+CD90-, and primitive fraction CD34+CD133+CD90+.

(F) Number of erythroid, myeloid, and mixed colonies generated in the CFU-C assay from HSPCs seeded on day 3 upon culture in different settings (n=6). Wilcoxon test.

(G) Number of erythroid, myeloid, and mixed colonies generated in the CFU-C assay from HSPCs seeded on 2D or 3D immediately after thawing or upon one or two days after initial 2D culture (n=6). Wilcoxon test.

(H) Representative gating strategy for the HSC-enriched single-cell differentiation assay. Colonies were considered in the analysis only if >30 cells were present in the following gates: Erythroid, Ery (CD45-GlyA+); Myeloid, My (CD45+CD11b+); Natural Killer, NK (CD45+CD56+CD11b-); Megakaryocyte, Meg (CD45+CD41+GlyA-).

(I,J) Percentage of different lineages within uni-lineage (I) or bi/multi-lineage (J) colonies generated in the single-cell differentiation assay.

(K) Representative gating strategy for PB, BM, and SP analyses. hCD45+ cells were identified within alive cells (7-AAD-). Within the human graft, cells were discriminated as B cells (CD45+CD19+), myeloid cells (CD45+CD19-CD13+), T cells (CD45+CD19-CD13-CD3+), HSPCs (CD45+CD19-CD13-CD3-CD34+) or other (CD45+CD19-CD13-CD3-CD34-).

(L-N) Percentage of human graft composition in the PB (L), BM (M), and SP (N) at the endpoint of transplanted mice (n=5). Mann-Whitney test.

Mean \pm SEM. *p < 0.05; **p < 0.01.

Figure S2

Figure S2. Nichoids remodel HSPC gene expression, reducing cell proliferation and DNA damage accumulation, related to Figure 2.

(A) Differentially expressed genes (FDR < 0.05) in 3D- vs. 2D-cultured HSPCs.

(B) Representative plot (left) and MFI (right) of CellTrace dye dilution on day 7 (n=6) in the HSC-enriched subset. Wilcoxon test.

(C) Representative plot of CellTrace dye dilution over time in bulk and HSC-enriched subsets. Values indicate the number of cell divisions performed by each cell in the highlighted peaks.

(D) Representative immunofluorescence staining (left) of DAPI (blue), pRPA (red), and γ H2AX (green) and number of DDR foci (right) per cell (more than 800 cells were analyzed for each condition). Median. Mann-Whitney test. Scale bars: 10 μ m.

(E) Representative gating strategy for p-p38 analyses.

(F) MFI of CellTrace dye dilution in bulk and HSC-enriched subsets on day 7 from freshly-isolated CB-derived HSPCs (n=6). Wilcoxon test.

(G) MFI of ROS measured by CellROX staining on day 7 from freshly-isolated CB-derived HSPCs (n=6). Wilcoxon test.

(H) MFI of 8-oxo-dG on day 7 from freshly-isolated CB-derived HSPCs (n=6). Wilcoxon test.

(I) Percentage of phospho-p38 (p-p38)-positive cells on day 7 from freshly-isolated CB-derived HSPCs (n=6). Wilcoxon test.

(J) Number of erythroid, myeloid, and mixed colonies generated in the CFU-C assay from freshly-isolated CB-derived HSPCs seeded on day 7 (n=6). Wilcoxon test.

Unless otherwise specified, Mean \pm SEM. *p < 0.05; **p < 0.01; ****p < 0.0001.

Figure S3

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Figure S3. Distinct 3D culture platforms may differentially regulate HSPC responses, related to Figure 2.

(A) Representative pictures of CD34+ cells cultured in spongostan scaffolds (left) and collagen-based spheroids (right). Scale bars: 100 μ m.

(B) Apoptosis analysis performed within CD34+ cells on day 7 (n=6).

(C) Percentage of phenotypically defined HSPC subsets on day 7 (n=6).

(D) MFI of CellTrace dye dilution in bulk and HSC-enriched subsets on day 7 (n=6). Wilcoxon test.

(E) MFI of ROS measured by CellROX staining in HSPCs on day 7 (n=6). Wilcoxon test.

(F) MFI of 8-oxo-dG in HSPCs on day 7 (n=6). Wilcoxon test.

(G) Quantification of single-strand and double-strand breaks by alkaline comet assay on day 7; each dot represents a single cell (more than 100 cells were analyzed for each condition). Median \pm 95% CI. Mann-Whitney test.

(H) Percentage of phospho-p38 (p-p38)-positive HSPCs on day 7 (n=6). Wilcoxon test.

(I) Representative immunofluorescence (left) showing tubulin spatial organization in HSPCs in spongostan scaffolds (top) and collagen-based spheroids (bottom), and tubulin score (right) on day 7. Dashed lines represent the tubulin score of HSPCs cultured in 2D (red) and nichoid (blue). Median Value. Mann-Whitney test. Scale bars: 10 μ m.

(J) Number of erythroid, myeloid, and mixed colonies generated in the CFU-C assay from HSPCs seeded on day 7 (n=6). Wilcoxon test.

Unless otherwise specified, Mean \pm SEM. *p < 0.05; **p < 0.01; ****p < 0.0001.

Figure S4

Figure S4. Nichoids enable efficient long-range gene editing, related to Figure 3.

- (A) Apoptosis analysis performed within CD34+ cells on day 4 (n=6).
- (B) Percentage of phenotypically defined HSPC subsets on day 4 (n=6).
- (C) Representative gating strategy for editing efficiency analysis. GFP+ cells were identified within CD34+ cells (gated within alive cells).
- (D) Percentage of edited cells within HSPC subsets on day 7 (n=6).
- (E) Percentage of edited alleles by HDR or non-homologous end joining (NHEJ) in HSPCs on day 7 (n=6).
- (F) Proliferation rate of HSPCs upon GE (GE=day 3, 24h post-editing=day 4, 96h post-editing=day 7). (n=6). Wilcoxon test (calculated at the last time point).
- (G) Representative plot (left) and percentage of HSPCs in indicated cell cycle phases (right) on day 3 (before GE) (n=4).
- (H) Apoptosis analysis performed within CD34+ cells on day 4 edited with Cas9/AAV6 plus GSE56 and Ad5-E4orf6/7 editing enhancers (n=4).
- (I) Percentage of phenotypically defined HSPC subsets on day 4 in cells edited with Cas9/AAV6 plus GSE56 and Ad5-E4orf6/7 editing enhancers (n=4).
- (J,K) Percentage of GFP+ cells in bulk (J) and HSPC subsets (K) on day 7 from cells edited with Cas9/AAV6 plus GSE56 and Ad5-E4orf6/7 editing enhancers (n=4).
- (L) Number of erythroid, myeloid, and mixed colonies generated in the CFU-C assay from cells edited with Cas9/AAV6 plus GSE56 and Ad5-E4orf6/7 editing enhancers seeded on day 4 (n=4).
- Mean \pm SEM. *p < 0.05.

Figure S5

Figure S5. Nichoids allow efficient GE across multiple engineering platforms and improve the engraftment of HDR-edited cells in serial transplantation experiments, related to Figure 3.

(A) Percentage of hCD45⁺ cells measured in the SP at the endpoint of transplanted mice (n=5). Mann-Whitney test.

(B) Representative gating strategy for GFP analyses in xenotransplantation experiments.

(C,D) Percentage of GFP⁺ cells (within hCD45⁺ cells) in the BM (C) and SP (D) at the endpoint of transplanted mice (n=5).

(E) Percentage of HDR-edited alleles by HDR from human cells measured in the BM at the endpoint of transplanted mice (n=5).

(F-H) Percentage of human graft composition in the PB (F), BM (G), and SP (H) at the endpoint of transplanted mice (n=5).

(I,J) Percentage of hCD45⁺ cells (I) and GFP⁺ cells (within hCD45⁺ cells) (J) measured in the SP at the endpoint of transplanted secondary recipients (n=8,6). Mann-Whitney test.

(K) Percentage of HDR-edited alleles by HDR from human cells measured in the BM at the endpoint of transplanted secondary recipients (n=8,6).

(L-N) Percentage of human graft composition in the PB (L), BM (M), and SP (N) at the endpoint of transplanted secondary recipients (n=8,6).

(O) Apoptosis analysis performed within CD34⁺ cells on day 4 edited with BE or PE (n=6).

(P) Percentage of phenotypically defined HSPC subsets on day 4 in cells edited with BE or PE (n=6).

(Q) Representative gating strategy for editing efficiency analysis. B2M-negative cells were identified within CD34⁺ cells (gated within alive cells).

(R) Percentage of B2M⁻ cells within HSPC subsets on day 7 (n=6).

(S) Representative Sanger Sequencing data from base- (left) and prime-edited cells on day 7 (right).

(T) Percentage of edited alleles on day 7 by Sanger Sequencing in HSPCs edited with BE or PE (n=6).

(U) Proliferation rate of HSPCs upon GE with BE or PE (GE=day 3, 24h post-editing=day 4, 96h post-editing=day 7). (n=6). Wilcoxon test (calculated at the last time point).

Mean ± SEM. *p < 0.05; **p < 0.01; ***p < 0.001.

Figure S6

Figure S6. Nichoids enable efficient LV-mediated gene addition, related to Figure 4.

- (A) Apoptosis analysis performed within CD34+ cells on day 2 (n=3).
- (B) Percentage of GFP+ cells within HSPC subsets on day 10 (n=6). Wilcoxon test.
- (C) VCN of transduced HSPCs on day 10 (n=6). Wilcoxon test.
- (D) Percentage of hCD45+ cells measured in the SP at the endpoint of transplanted mice (n=7). Mann-Whitney test.
- (E,F) Percentage of GFP+ cells (within hCD45+ cells) in the BM (E) and SP (F) at the endpoint of transplanted mice (n=7).
- (G-I) Percentage of human graft composition in the PB (G), BM (H), and SP (I) at the endpoint of transplanted mice (n=7). Mann-Whitney test.
- (J) Number of unique integrations from IS analyses. Mann-Whitney test.
- (K) Tracking and relative abundance of ISs reported over time in transplanted mice (A=2D group, B=3D group). Each colored bar univocally identifies an IS with >1% representation in at least one time point, with its abundance proportional to the height of the bar; a colored ribbon connects two neighboring time points for each recaptured clone. The total number of unique ISs is reported on each bar.
- (L) IS gene frequency and CIS analysis in transplanted mice (A=2D group, B=3D group). Each dot represents a gene, labeled with the corresponding color if observed as significant. The dashed line is the alpha value 0.05. Grubbs test.
- Mean \pm SEM. *p < 0.05; **p < 0.01; ***p < 0.001.

Figure S7

Figure S7. Nichoids increase the engraftment and clonal complexity of WAS patient-derived HSPCs upon gene addition, related to Figure 5.

(A) Apoptosis analysis performed within CD34+ cells on day 3 (n=6).

(B) Percentage of phenotypically defined HSPC subsets on day 3 (n=6).

(C) VCN of transduced HSPCs on day 10 (n=6).

(D) VCN of transduced HSPCs from healthy donors according to the transduction protocol described in Figure 5A, in the presence or absence of retronectin (n=6). Wilcoxon test.

(E) VCN of human cells measured in the BM at the endpoint of transplanted mice (n=5). Random-intercept LME model.

(F-H) Percentage of human graft composition in the PB (F), BM (G), and SP (H) at the endpoint of transplanted mice (n=5). Random-intercept LME models.

(I) Number of unique integrations from IS analyses. Random-intercept LME model.

(J) Tracking and relative abundance of ISs reported over time in transplanted mice (A=2D group, B=3D group). Each colored bar univocally identifies an IS with >1% representation in at least one time point, with its abundance proportional to the height of the bar; a colored ribbon connects two neighboring time points for each recaptured clone. The total number of unique ISs is reported on each bar.

(K) IS gene frequency and CIS analysis in transplanted mice (A=2D group, B=3D group). Each dot represents a gene, labeled with the corresponding color if observed as significant. The dashed line is the alpha value 0.05. Grubbs test.

Mean \pm SEM. *p < 0.05; **p < 0.01; ***p < 0.001.